

SELF- MANAGEMENT AND INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES TOWARD SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The respondents of this study were the one hundred and fifty (100) teachers from Sto. Anghel District, Division of San Pablo City. The questionnaire was used as the main data-gathering instrument. Taking into consideration the gathered data, the following important findings were summarized as follows: the respondents perceived that self-management in terms of self-monitoring as “always observed”, while self-management in terms of self-evaluating as “often observed”. the respondents perceived instructional practices in terms of teaching-learning activities, teachers’ strategies, and teachers’ collaborative practices as “always observed”. On the other hand, special assignment/ designation and use of ICT were assessed by the respondents as “often observed”. Further, the level of school effectiveness as to students’ outcomes, community involvement, work motivation/ awards as “often observed”, while professional growth and development was construed as “always observed”. Further, all of the respondents’ responses reveals that self-management showed correlation with school effectiveness. Clearly, self-monitoring and self-evaluating were found to be significantly related with students’ outcomes, community involvement, professional growth and development and work motivation/ awards. Likewise, students’ outcomes, community involvement, professional growth and development and work motivation/ awards were found to be significantly related with all of the instructional practices variables such as teaching-learning activities, teachers’ strategies, teachers’ collaborative practices, special assignment/ designation, and use of ICT. On the basis of the earlier findings, the following conclusions are set forth: The results revealed significant relationship between the teacher self-management and instructional practices. The null hypothesis is not sustained. Based on these findings, the researcher recommends a much stronger support to the self-management and instructional practices from the DepEd policy makers through the formulation of guidelines and policies regarding the development of teachers to further strengthen school effectiveness. This could be done by aligning the programs for teachers towards the benefit of the learners.

Keywords: Self-management, instructional practices, school effectiveness